

Regional characterization of the vulnerability of the unconfined groundwaters in Bulgaria

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Abstract. Groundwater vulnerability to contaminant infiltration from the surface, and to state deterioration, is related to the spatial distribution of rocks with diverse porosities, flow characteristics and unsaturated zone thickness. For the present regional assessment of groundwater vulnerability, it is considered most appropriate to adopt a method based on spatial differences in the geological and tectonic, and related hydrogeological, conditions in Bulgaria. The objective of the present study is to compile a vulnerability map of the unconfined groundwater in the country. This groundwater type is very important for drinking water supply, and it is at the highest risk of contamination. The groundwater on the territory of the Republic of Bulgaria has been divided into seven vulnerability classes, based on the corresponding hydrogeological units. The map is based on the geological map of Bulgaria in scale 1:100 000. It shows that groundwater is of low vulnerability over a large part of the country's area (57%). Medium to medium-high groundwater vulnerability is defined for approximately 31% of the total area, while high and very high vulnerability are defined for 7% and 5%, correspondingly.

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INTRODUCTION

Compared to surface water, groundwater is a much more reliable source for water supply as it is better protected against external influence, both natural and anthropogenic. The degree of protection depends on many factors, the more important of them being diverse conditions of formation, groundwater flow and specific interaction between the porous medium and the various properties of potential contaminants. Compiling groundwater vulnerability maps is a method for visualizing the spatial complexity of the influence exerted by these and other factors. The term “vulnerability” was introduced in the end-1960s by the French hydrogeologist J. Mar-

gat, according to Vrba and Zaporozec (1994), who provided the following definition: “Vulnerability is an intrinsic property of a groundwater system that depends on the sensitivity of that system to human and/or natural impacts.” Various methods have been developed for compiling vulnerability maps, depending on the scale, character and type of the water-bearing structures, the conditions of recharge and groundwater flow, as well as factors that influence them.

As unconfined groundwater is very important for drinking water supply and is at the highest risk of contamination, the objective of the present study is to compile a generalized map of unconfined groundwater vulnerability in scale 1:100 000, based

on the analysis of up-to-date geological and hydrogeological information.

PREVIOUS STUDIES OF GROUNDWATER VULNERABILITY IN BULGARIA

Vrba and Zaporozec (1994) divided the approaches to map groundwater vulnerability into three main categories, based on the investigated area, geological and hydrogeological setting, and the amount and quality of necessary information. Approaches from all three categories have been applied in Bulgaria.

The first category of mapping approaches is based on analysis of the spatial differences in geological and physiographical conditions in terms of groundwater formation and flow, in both the saturated and unsaturated zones. Most often, these approaches are applied to small-scale maps in regional assessments of groundwater vulnerability. Antonov and Raikova (1978) proposed a methodology for compiling a groundwater vulnerability map of Bulgaria in scale 1:200 000, taking into account the exceptionally complex and diverse geological, and consequently hydrogeological, conditions in the country. That methodology was applied to one map sheet (Vratsa) of the geological map (Raikova *et al.*, 1983), and to a smaller area in the catchment of the Vit River (Benderev *et al.*, 1992). Similar methodology (according to unpublished data of the Ministry of Environment and Water) has been applied for the groundwater vulnerability in Bulgaria in scale 1:500 000, based on the geological map in the corresponding scale.

The second category of approaches is based on combining selected parameters, which characterize various natural factors affecting groundwater vulnerability. Each parameter is assessed in terms of its significance for the total estimate of vulnerability. The natural range of each parameter is subdivided into intervals and each interval is assigned a value. The vulnerability is evaluated by summing up the products of the interval rating and the weight for each parameter used in the evaluation. The end result is a number representing an overall value of groundwater vulnerability to contamination. Following this methodology, various approaches have been proposed, depending on the parameters used for describing different factors affecting the hydrogeological conditions and the prospects for contaminant migration (Moges and Dinka, 2022). Two of the methods that belong to this approach category have been applied in Bulgaria. One of them is DRASTIC, which requires the following input pa-

rameters: depth to groundwater, recharge rate, aquifer, soil, topography, vadose zone's impact, and aquifer's hydraulic conductivity. It has been applied for individual hydrogeological units, *e.g.*, parts of the Upper Thracian Plain (Petkov and Petrov, 2005), the Sofia Basin (Petrov, 2004), the Ogosta River catchment (Orehova *et al.*, 2009), the Danubian lowlands (Benderev, 2014), and the Sarmatian aquifer in northeast Bulgaria (Pavlova *et al.*, 2016). Stoyanova (2015) proposed a version of this method to account for the probability of arsenic contamination in the alluvial aquifer at the upper range of the Ogosta River. The other approach that has been applied is EPIK, which uses parameters related to epikarst, protective cover, infiltration conditions, and the degree of karst network development. It is applicable for assessing the groundwater vulnerability in karst and has been used for the Western Balkan Mts. (Mihaylova *et al.*, 2009) and the transborder karst basins between Bulgaria and Serbia (Benderev *et al.*, 2016).

The third approach category is based on applying analytical and numerical models that account for actual conditions and allow for obtaining most reliable results. They are currently widely used in hydrogeology worldwide, including Bulgaria (Stoyanov, 2019).

METHODS

The present map of unconfined groundwater vulnerability in Bulgaria has been compiled following the approach proposed by Antonov and Raikova (1978) and Raikova *et al.* (1983), who used the hydrogeological map in scale 1:200 000. That approach is considered most appropriate for regional assessment, and it has been further developed and complemented in accordance with more recent concepts for this type of mapping (Vrba and Zaporozec, 1994; Moges and Dinka, 2022), advances in the knowledge of groundwater and related topics in the last 40 years in Bulgaria, as well as GIS becoming a standard tool. The completed geological mapping in scale 1:100 000 is of significant importance for updating the ideas about groundwater formation, spatial distribution of rocks with different permeability, flow characteristics, and risk of potential pollution. The results of that mapping are compiled by the Japan International Cooperation Agency (JICA) (2008) in a geodatabase, associated with water management in the country. The spatial distribution of the different rock varieties provides information about a number of hydrogeological factors affect-

ing groundwater vulnerability: properties related to groundwater flow and contaminant migration; potential for recharge, flow and discharge; interconnectivity between different hydrogeological units; etc. Along with the geological information, the geodatabase also includes several other important layers related to different natural and anthropogenic conditions and factors, such as terrain, soils, hydrologic conditions, anthropogenic influence. When compiling the present map, each of the initially distinguished categories was assigned a degree of vulnerability, as previously adopted by the majority of authors. Seven classes are distinguished in terms of groundwater vulnerability to pollutants from the surface:

1) Very high vulnerability corresponds to Category I vulnerability as defined by Raikova *et al.* (1983). It comprises karst areas and outcrops of intensely karstified rocks (limestones, dolostones, marbles), with common karst forms on the surface and underground, and well-developed conduit network. This category also includes the typical karst basins characterized by rapid groundwater flow between recharge and discharge zones. Within such areas, potential contaminants from the surface reach the drainage zones in very short time and with little retention. This class also comprises outcrops of karstified rocks in the areas of occurrence of platform type karst, where aquifers of significant groundwater resource are formed. Most vulnerable are the intensely karstified ranges along the river valleys incised in the unsaturated zones of the aquifers.

2) High vulnerability is a class comprising areas of carbonate rocks that are relatively less karstified, as a result of various factors, *e.g.*, components and layers that are not affected by karst formation. The groundwater flow takes place mainly in dissolution fractures; however, the flow rate is not as high as in the wide karst channels. Similar high vulnerability is also typical for the porous-karst collectors in Neogene organogenic limestones, which have high primary porosity. Raikova *et al.* (1983) included in this class the top parts of talus cones on mountain slopes, where the coarse unconsolidated materials (boulders, gravels, and sands) are predominant. These are characterized by high permeability decreasing towards the base and along the direction of surface water and groundwater flow as a result of decreasing particle size and accumulation of clayey interlayers.

3) Medium to high vulnerability is typical for unconsolidated sediments in river terraces, where the accumulated pore water is in direct connection

with the surface water. Normally, the alluvial deposits are structured in two layers: lower layer of sands and gravels, and upper layer of sandy clays, which inhibits the infiltration of contaminants. Usually, the groundwater is shallow and hydraulically connected to the river. Raikova *et al.* (1983) included in this class sandy loess deposits as well, in which vertical inhomogeneity is typical as a result of buried soils. Nevertheless, due to the presence of micropores, these deposits are characterized by relatively high infiltration rates of rainwater. Medium to high groundwater vulnerability is likewise typical for the outcrops of Neogene sands forming the recharge zones for deeper aquifers.

4) Medium vulnerability is representative of pore water in unconsolidated sediments of Neogene and Quaternary age and in the clayey loess in North Bulgaria. These are represented by irregularly alternating sands, clays, and other sediments. The presence of low-permeability deposits inhibits the infiltration of contaminants. Commonly, there is a gradual transition between such sediments and overlying alluvium. This vulnerability class also comprises the lower levels of talus cones, where the clayey component increases with depth, consequently decreasing the overall permeability and providing protection to groundwater.

5) Medium to low vulnerability corresponds to Category V of Raikova *et al.* (1983). It refers to outcrops of fractured aquifers in volcanic-sedimentary complexes, as well as in alternating sedimentary terrigenous, terrigenous-carbonate and carbonate rocks. In such sequences, as the result of dissimilar modes of fracturing and dissolution, there are conditions for forming fracture-layered hydrogeological structures, where layers of different permeability and migration capacity occur. This vulnerability type also includes aquifers in rocks of relatively high porosity, such as rhyolites and weathered granitoids.

6) Low groundwater vulnerability corresponds to Category VI of Raikova *et al.* (1983) and it refers to outcrops of fractured aquifers, which have relatively uniform composition and are less susceptible to weathering than the aquifers included in the previous type. Similarly to the medium to low groundwater vulnerability type, the low vulnerability is associated with groundwater accumulated in zones of weathering and tectonic fracturing of rocks of different ages and origin. In such aquifers, the groundwater volume is highest near the surface and gradually decreases with depth. The groundwater flow direction follows the terrain, from the elevated parts towards the base level. For that reason, poten-

tial groundwater contamination could not spread over a wide area, and it would be constrained to one slope of a single catchment. The contaminant migration would be in one direction only, and it would be limited by the base level. The velocity of migration would depend on many factors and could vary in a wide range, which is why the groundwater vulnerability is distinguished according to aquifer types.

7) Very low vulnerability corresponds to Category VII of Raikova *et al.* (1983), and it is characteristic of groundwater in outcrops of rocks with low permeability, such as clays, marls, and phyllites. Contaminant infiltration and migration in those aquifers is impeded by the low permeability and sorption capacity.

Only groundwater in outcropping aquifers was taken into consideration when compiling the groundwater vulnerability map. The boundaries correspond to the geological map of Bulgaria in scale 1:100 000. Therefore, the degree of vulnerability has not been determined for unconfined groundwater that formed in covered karst aquifers.

Such is the case with some typical karst basins in the Balkan Mountains (*e.g.*, Maragidik, Lovech-Tarnovo, Iskrets, and Milanovo) and some karst aquifers, mostly in northeast Bulgaria. The most typical of the latter is the Aptian–Barremian aquifer, which contains significant groundwater resources of economic importance. Most of its area is covered by loess and other Neogene–Quaternary deposits. Outcrops of karstified limestone occur only in the deeply incised river valleys, and these are classified as zones of very high groundwater vulnerability. Groundwater vulnerability assessment of such regions requires the use of different local approaches.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A new map in scale 1:100 000 of unconfined groundwater vulnerability was compiled (Fig. 1), and it can be used for regional analyses and assessments. The analysis of the map indicates that groundwaters in Bulgaria are characterized by different degrees of

Fig. 1. Map of unconfined groundwater vulnerability in Bulgaria.

vulnerability. The most common classes of groundwater vulnerability are medium to low (approximately 30%) and low (approximately 19%) (see Fig. 2). Most of these were found in mountainous areas, where the anthropogenic influence is relatively small. Exceptions are some areas in southeast Bulgaria, where volcanogenic sedimentary rocks and flysch successions occur. Groundwater of very low vulnerability occurs in approximately 8% of the country's territory, where it is associated with clayey Quaternary and Neogene sediments or Mesozoic marls in North Bulgaria, and phyllites and schists in the Western Balkan Mountains. Less than medium groundwater vulnerability occurs in overall 57% of the area. Despite the low vulnerability of such groundwater, the prospects are typically not good for construction of wells with high abstraction rate.

Medium vulnerability (14%) is assigned to groundwater in alternating sandy and clayey deposits of Neogene age to the north of the Balkan Mountains or in the tectonic graben-like depressions in South Bulgaria. The relative protection of such groundwater, as well as good yield and permeability of the sandy interlayers, makes it an important source for water supply, even for large cities like Sofia and Plovdiv.

Groundwater of medium to high vulnerability (approximately 17%) occurs mainly in alluvial deposits, and it is subject to intense abstraction. Simultaneously, the river terraces are subject to considerable anthropogenic influence. Many settlements, farming lands, industrial sites, and quarries are located on river terraces. This makes it neces-

sary to locally undertake more detailed future investigations of vulnerability. The rest of aquifers with unconfined groundwater of the same vulnerability class have less economic importance.

The classes of high and very high groundwater vulnerability cover 12% of the country's territory, out of which only 5% is very high. This category includes groundwater in typical karst basins in the Balkan Mountains, the mountains of Pirin, Rhodopes, Strandzha, the Kraishte region, and the Fore-Balkan Mts. They usually discharge from large karst springs, which are important sources of household and drinking water supply in many towns, *e.g.*, Vratsa, Pleven, Lovech, Smolyan, Troyan, Kotel, Bansko, and numerous other settlements. Potential contaminants could reach consumers very quickly and in high concentrations because of the wide occurrence of surficial and underground karst forms in the recharge zones and a well-developed network of channels and galleries. It is beneficial that the recharge zones are located in mountainous regions with little human influence. The only exception are the karst basins in Upper Cretaceous limestones of the Fore-Balkan Mts, where the same vulnerability class includes groundwater in the outcrops of karstified limestone on the slopes and bottoms of river valleys in North Bulgaria. These form the recharge zones of two of the most important aquifers in Bulgaria: the Upper Jurassic–Lower Cretaceous and the Barremian–Aptian aquifers. In some valleys, the river flow is completely lost. In addition, agriculture is intensely developed in the river catchments in these regions.

Regionally, the class of high groundwater vulnerability has limited occurrence, approximately 7% of the country's territory. According to the applied methodology, this class has been assigned to groundwater in less karstified rocks, which have relatively limited occurrence. These comprise some isolated areas in the Balkan and Fore-Balkan Mountains. The outcrops of the Neogene organogenic limestones (mostly Sarmatian in age) in the platform part of northwest and northeast Bulgaria have larger regional occurrence. The karst formation is primarily associated with enlargement of the pore space between the unconsolidated deposited shells. This determines the porous-karst character of the aquifer, whereas typical unconfined aquifers formed, in which potential contaminants could easily infiltrate from the surface. Seawater intrusions have been established in the coastal zone of the Sarmatian aquifer outcrops in northeast Bulgaria, thus confirming the groundwater vulnerability. The elevated parts of the talus cones in the periphery of

Fig. 2. Share of areas with different groundwater vulnerability in Bulgaria.

the graben-like depressions in South Bulgaria have also been assigned to high groundwater vulnerability. The degree of vulnerability gradually decreases towards the cone bases, as a result of the presence, and increasing density, of clayey interlayers.

CONCLUSION

The present newly compiled vulnerability map of unconfined water in Bulgaria, based on the geological map in scale 1:100 000, indicates various degrees of groundwater vulnerability in the country. It is established that the groundwater is of relatively lower vulnerability for the greater part of the total area of the country. High and very high vulnerability classes are established over very small areas. It is recommended to use the digital information to establish the anthropogenic impact in the zones with different groundwater vulnerability. This would help identifying regions where it would be necessary to carry out additional investigations aimed at protecting the

water resources. Alluvial aquifers where the groundwater vulnerability class is medium to high shall be given special attention, considering these are important sources for water supply. It is necessary to undertake detailed vulnerability assessments in these areas, applying parametric methods or modeling. Such methods need to be applied to karst basins, covered partially or totally, or unconfined aquifers.

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